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D3.1 BEST PRACTICES FOR COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF CITIZEN SCIENCE DATA INFRASTRUCTURES

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31.07.2023

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Acknowledgment

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Reference

Please cite this work as:

Soacha, K., Álvarez, A, Cardenas, A. (2023), European Citizen Science: D3.1 Best practices for collaborative development of citizen science data infrastructures, ICM-CSIC, Barcelona.

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Document Identification Sheet

Project Ref. No.	101058509
Project acronym	ECS
Project Full Name	European Citizen Science
Document Name	ECS_D3.1_Best practices for collaborative development of citizen science data infrastructures_20230721.pdf
Dissemination Level	PU
Contractual Date of Delivery	Month 12, 31.07.2023
Actual Date of Delivery	31 July 2023
Type	R – Document, report
Deliverable number	D3.1
Deliverable name	Best Practices for Collaborative Development of Citizen Science Data Infrastructures
WP / Lead Beneficiary	WP3 / T3.1 / ICM-CSIC
Number of pages	57
Authors	Karen Soacha, Ana Álvarez and Amalia Cardenas (ICM-CSIC)
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Reviewers	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA)
Project Officer	Irina Elena Tiron
Abstract	The best practices report offers a literature review of collaborative initiatives for co-designing and co-developing citizen science data infrastructures. It provides valuable insights into practices, lessons learned, and resources structured under the lifecycle data management framework. The review covers experiences from citizen science projects related to data collection, data governance, data ethics, and data quality. It highlights critical aspects from the infrastructure perspective on data collection, data sharing agreements, and ethical guidelines, and emphasises the importance of data interoperability and quality assurance.
Keywords	ECS, data infrastructures, data services, co-design, co-development, citizen science, open source.

Version Log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
0.1	20230401	Karen Soacha (ICM-CSIC)	Creation of the document structure and methodology
0.2	20230516	Ana Álvarez and Amalia Cárdenas (ICM-CSIC)	Inclusion of literature review results: proven practices, lessons learned and key resources from literature review
0.3	20230525	Karen Soacha (ICM-CSIC)	Inclusion of contents (methodology, framework, case study), revision of literature review and creation of the first version
0.4	20230614	Jorge Barba (IBERCIVIS), Muki Haklay (UP), Miguel Hernández (SfC), Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA)	First review by WP3 members
0.5	20230711	Karen Soacha, Ana Álvarez and Amalia Cárdenas (ICM-CSIC)	Processing of feedback by WP3 members and preparation of final first version
0.6	20230717	Claudia Fabó Cartas (ECSA)	Second peer-review
1.0	20230724	Karen Soacha (ICM-CSIC)	Release of final first version

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List of definitions and acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
API	Application Programming Interface
CBM	Community-Based Monitoring
CS	Citizen Science
CSI	Citizen Science Initiatives
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ECS	European Citizen Science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FPIC	Free, prior and informed consent
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
JBIF	Japan Biodiversity Information Facility
IPR	Intellectual property rights
IT	Information Technology
OSS	Open-Source Software
PID	Persistent Identifier
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/Quality Control
R&I	Research & Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
ORI	Open Research Infrastructure
PID	Personal Identifiable Data
PPSR	Public Participation in Scientific Research
SDG(s)	Sustainable Development Goal (s)
SDIs	Spatial Data Infrastructures
SDLM	Science Data Lifecycle Model

STS	Science and Technology Studies
URL	Uniform Resource Locator (i.e. colloquially, a web address)

Definitions

Co-design: approach that enables a wide range of people to contribute to problem formulation and solution in a creative manner. The co-design process places users at the centre, considering them as experts of their own experience and incorporating their needs and concerns into the design process [1].

Darwin Core: extension of Dublin Core for biodiversity informatics. It is meant to provide a stable standard reference for sharing information on biological diversity [2].

Dataset: collection of data gathered by a project using a single sampling protocol (data collection method) [2].

Data infrastructure: the underlying framework and components necessary for the collection, storage, management, and dissemination of data in a structured and efficient manner [3].

Data service: range of offerings, technologies, and processes designed to support the efficient management, processing, and utilisation of data [3].

Data standardisation: data representable in a uniform and common structure and format [4].

Dublin Core: a set of fifteen "core" elements for describing resources. It was originally developed for a digital "library card catalogue" for the Web (Wikipedia). It is now commonly used as the basis of metadata for many catalogues [2].

ISO: International Organization for Standardization, who has established some standards for data quality for different domains [5].

Metadata: data that describes data, it accompanies the research data which makes it discoverable and usable over time [6].

Ontology: formal specification of a conceptualization; renders shared vocabulary and taxonomy which models a domain with the definition of objects and/or concepts and their properties and relations; the representation of entities, ideas, and events, along with their properties and relations, according to a system of categories [7].

Standard: data and procedure that provide a common language which allows similar information from disparate sources to be efficiently aggregated and exchanged, thus giving raw data potential value, utility, and impact beyond the purpose for which it was originally collected [8].

Executive Summary

The "Best Practices for Collaborative Development of Citizen Science Data Infrastructures" report, conducted as part of Work Package 3, aims to review collaborative initiatives for co-designing and co-developing data services in citizen science projects. The review focuses on lessons learned from past and ongoing projects to establish best practices for different stages of design and development. The report encompasses technical and ethical frameworks, including seven sections and guiding principles. It identifies proven practices and lessons learned while providing key resources for co-designing citizen science data infrastructures and data services.

The review includes various aspects of collaborative development, data collection, data standards, data quality assurance, data accessibility, data ownership, policy, and ethics. Special attention has been given to the unique considerations of citizen science initiatives, such as ethics and data privacy. The report is intended for wide dissemination among ECS stakeholders. It serves as a valuable training resource for the European Citizen Science project, supporting the implementation of digital skills, the European Citizen Science Academy, and other training activities.

1. Context

The purpose of the document is to offer a quick list of aspects to consider when planning the development of technological services in citizen science. However, it can be used at any time as a checklist for existing infrastructure or projects that have already been implemented. In turn, it is intended as part of a set of training resources for digital skills for the citizen science community. Especially as an introductory resource that can be expanded through the key resources that are proposed in each thematic section. It is aimed at managers of data infrastructures, developers, project coordinators of citizen science initiatives, and people involved in the development and implementation of technological services in citizen science.

The report compiles best practices, also called proven practices, and lessons learned from citizen science and open science initiatives, projects, and platforms for the collaborative development of citizen science data infrastructure. Citizen science data infrastructure is understood as technology-based platforms, tools and services used to collect, store, manage, process, share, visualise and analyse information (data and metadata), as well as those used to organise and manage citizen science projects and events [3]. Data infrastructure includes datasets, the technology, training, and processes that make them usable, policies and regulations such as those for data sharing and protection, and the organisations and people that collect, maintain, and use data [9].

To undertake the search and classification of practices, a conceptual framework was established to guide the categorisation process. The selected framework was the high-level science data lifecycle model (SDLM) described in section two. Based on this framework, the practices were organised into seven thematic sections. In addition to the conceptual framework, an ethical framework was deemed necessary, leading to the incorporation of a core set of values and guiding principles, primarily drawn from the concepts of open science, open data, and open infrastructure, including FAIR data principles detailed in section three.

The practices documented in this report stem from experiences and implemented projects within the context of collaborative initiatives and citizen science. They were classified according to the data lifecycle model. As co-design and co-development are central pillars of this report, it includes a case study documentation from the Cos4Cloud project, which aimed to co-design technological services for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Section four outlines the methodological approach of the project, including the co-design framework utilised, the workshops structure and the communication and engagement strategy implemented to facilitate the co-design of technological services.

Section five provides a detailed methodology for the literature review. It describes the data sources used and the defined criteria for selecting the documents analysed, from which the best practices and lessons learned were extracted. Ultimately, the selected practices were derived from the review of 65 documents. Within the scope of this report, the term proven practices is adopted. Proven practices, also known as 'best practices' or 'good practices,' are effective methods that can be replicated in different contexts, underlining the importance of learning and adapting practices that suit the environment. Lessons learned capture insights from experiences, including what worked, what did not work, problem-solving methods, and key insights, while proven practices focus on successful approaches. To ensure clarity and ease of understanding for the reader, lessons learned in this report are mainly focused on what did not work while proven practices on what worked.

Lastly, section six compiles the identified proven practices, serving as a culmination of the report's findings and insights. The practices are organised into seven thematic sections that respond to data cycle management. The thematic sections are: data infrastructure, data services, data collection, data standards, data quality assurance, data accessibility, data ownership, policy, and ethics. Each section includes a selected compilation of proven practices, lessons learned and key resources. Key resources are documents that contain widely accepted practices and recommendations for developing components of data infrastructure, consolidating validated theoretical and practical references.

It is important to emphasise that the purpose of this report, as a training resource, is to provide an introductory overview of proven practices. For more detailed information on implementation or to expand upon the practices, it is necessary to refer to direct sources of information or the additional resources proposed, such as guidelines, instructional materials, and more. This report serves as a starting point to familiarise oneself with the key concepts, principles, and practices, while further resources provide the necessary guidance for practical implementation.

Finally, the report encompasses essential considerations that illuminate the primary findings of the review. These considerations offer insights and serve as a stepping stone for future analysis, specifically in identifying and implementing practices necessary within the realm of citizen science data infrastructures.

2. Framework: Data Lifecycle

For the purpose of this report and inspired by the paper 'Best practices for data management in citizen science: an Indian outlook' [10], the practices are structured in thematic sections connected to the high-level Science Data Lifecycle Model (SDLM) to illustrate how data management activities relate to citizen science data workflows, infrastructures, and services.

Fig. 1 The Science Data Life Cycle Model has primary and cross-cutting elements that help determine action at different stages of data collection, preservation, and analyses. Primary elements include planning, acquiring, processing, analysing, preserving, and publishing data, while the cross-cutting elements run parallelly throughout the data life cycle and involve describing metadata, managing data quality, and data security/backup. The primary elements of the data life cycle can be further mapped to ‘before’ data acquisition (pink arrow), ‘during’ a project (orange arrow), and ‘after’ data are acquired (green arrows) [10].

The Science Data Lifecycle Model (SDLM) provides a framework for understanding and managing data throughout its lifecycle. The SDLM consists of six primary elements: plan, acquire, process, analyse, preserve, and publish/share. These elements correspond to the organisation of mapping proven practices, which are structured into seven sections: data infrastructure, data services, data collection, data standards, data quality assurance, data accessibility, and data ownership, policy, and ethics. The practices within each section are strategically organised to align with the steps of the data lifecycle.

The **first section, data infrastructure**, focuses on the necessary technological and physical resources to support data management and storage. It involves setting up hardware, software, and networks to facilitate data acquisition, processing, and preservation. This step ensures that the data lifecycle can proceed smoothly by providing a reliable foundation for the subsequent stages. The **second section, data services**, encompasses the development of tools, systems, and services that enable effective data management. It involves creating platforms for data sharing, collaboration, and dissemination. Data services aim to enhance accessibility, discoverability, and usability of the data, supporting the later stages of analysis and publication.

The **third section, data collection**, involves the systematic acquisition of data from various sources, such as experiments, observations, or surveys. This step ensures that relevant data is gathered according to predefined objectives and requirements, aligning with the initial planning phase of the SDLM. The **fourth section, data standards**, addresses the need for consistent and interoperable data formats, metadata, and vocabularies. By

adhering to established standards, data can be easily exchanged, integrated, and compared across different research projects and disciplines. Data standards facilitate the processing and analysis stages of the SDLM, enabling meaningful insights and reliable results. The **fifth section, data quality assurance**, focuses on ensuring the accuracy, completeness, and reliability of the collected data. This includes validating data, identifying and addressing errors or inconsistencies, and applying quality control measures. Data quality assurance is crucial for trustworthy analysis and subsequent decision-making.

The **sixth section, data accessibility**, emphasises making data available to the intended users or stakeholders. It involves establishing appropriate access controls, licensing, and data sharing policies to balance data openness with privacy and security concerns. Data accessibility enables transparency, reproducibility, and broader collaboration within the scientific community. **The final section, data ownership, policy, and ethics**, addresses legal and ethical considerations surrounding data management. It encompasses issues of intellectual property, data rights, privacy, confidentiality, and ethical conduct. Policies and guidelines are developed to ensure responsible data handling and to protect the rights and interests of data creators, contributors, and subjects.

By organising the practices within the seven sections and incorporating the transversal areas of data services and data infrastructures, the mapping of proven practices aligns with the steps of the SDLM, ensuring comprehensive coverage and effective management of data throughout its lifecycle.

In addition to the technical framework, it is necessary to consider an ethical framework that offers fundamental values and principles when approaching ethical challenges. Some of the most representative ethical frameworks in the context of open research infrastructures are presented in the following section.

3. Core values and guiding principles

The co-design of data infrastructures and data services is a collaborative and iterative process that requires careful consideration of ethical implications. To ensure responsible and inclusive development, it is crucial to establish an ethical framework that sets principles and values to guide the implementation of co-design efforts. Several key principles and values have emerged in the realm of open science and data management, providing a foundation for ethical data infrastructure and service co-design. These include the Open Science core values and guiding principles, which emphasise transparency, accessibility, and collaboration. Additionally, the Principles for Strengthening Our Data Infrastructure by the Open Data Institute outline key aspects such as interoperability, usability, and sustainability. Other influential principles in this domain include the principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure, the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) [13], and the Ten Principles of Citizen Science [14]. By embracing these principles and values, stakeholders can navigate the co-design process ethically, fostering an environment that promotes equitable access, responsible data management, and the advancement of knowledge for the benefit of all.

3.1 Open science core values and guiding principles

The **UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science** [11] published in 2021 is the first international standard-setting instrument on open science. The document proposes a series of core values and guiding

principles. The core values of open science stem from the rights-based, ethical, epistemological, economic, legal, political, social, multi-stakeholder and technological implications of opening science to society and broadening the principles of openness to the whole cycle of scientific research. The core values and principles are listed below:

Values

- **Quality and integrity** ensuring that science is high-quality and scrutinised by bringing together different sources of knowledge and making evaluation of scientific methods and outputs more transparent and accurate.
- **Collective benefit** recognising that science is a global public good that belongs to all of humanity.
- **Equity and fairness** ensuring equitable, fair, and reciprocal access to science for all producers and consumers of knowledge regardless of their location, nationality, race, age, gender, income, socio-economic circumstance, career stage, discipline, language, religion, disability, ethnicity, migratory status or any other grounds.
- **Diversity and inclusiveness** embracing diversity of knowledge, practices, workflows, languages and research topics and outputs.

Guiding principles

- **Transparency, scrutiny, critique, and reproducibility** to reinforce the rigour of scientific results, enhance the positive impact of science on society, and increase society's ability to solve complex interconnected problems.
- **Equality of opportunities** to ensure that all scientists and those with an interest in science have equal opportunity to access, contribute to and benefit from science, regardless of origin or circumstance.
- **Responsibility, respect and accountability** to be responsible for and aware of public accountability, potential conflicts of interest, intellectual integrity, and the possible social or ecological consequences of research activities.
- **Collaboration, participation and inclusion** to ensure that scientific collaborations transcend the boundaries of geography, language and resources, and include knowledge from marginalised communities to solve problems of great social importance.
- **Flexibility to acknowledge** that there is no one-size-fits-all way to practise open science and to encourage different pathways to practising it while upholding the core values.
- **Sustainability** to be as efficient and impactful as possible by building on long-term practices, services, infrastructures, and funding models to ensure participation of scientists from less-privileged countries or institutions.

Fig. 2. UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science at a Glance. The Recommendation on Open Science, the first international standard-setting instrument on open science, was adopted by 193 countries in November 2021 at the 41st session of the UNESCO General Conference. The Recommendation provides an internationally agreed definition and a set of shared values and guiding principles for open science. It also identifies a set of actions conducive to a fair and equitable operationalisation of open science for all at the individual, institutional, national, regional, and international levels) [11].

3.2 Principles for strengthening our data infrastructure

The Open Data Institute published the principles for data infrastructure [9] and also the principles for personal data [12] in 2016. The personal data principles will help to build services and find insights in ways that people can understand and trust. Data infrastructure provides a foundation that allows those services and insights to

flourish. The following data infrastructure principles should be used when that foundation is being designed, built and assessed:

1. Design for open: Open data, open culture, open standards, open source, and collaborative models build trust, reduce cost and create more value than other approaches. Being open improves quality as more people can contribute to the outcome and increases the number of connections that can be made. Data benefits from network effects: it creates more value as more people use, contribute to, and maintain it.

2. Build with the web: We need to learn how to publish, discover, use and link together data across the web. Data on and in the web is continuing to grow with more devices being connected and interconnected every day. The billions of people, sensors and services on the web produce and use data. Data infrastructure must support the web of data.

3. Respect privacy: In the most impactful and valuable data infrastructure, openness is maximised but what is private remains private. Different countries have their own data protection legislation and social contracts, which need to be adhered to. To build trust, organisations using personal data should also be open with people about how they use and share that data.

4. Benefit everyone: Data infrastructure components should be designed and supported to benefit as many stakeholders as may use it. Everyone should benefit from the innovation, services, and insights that the whole data infrastructure allows. Sometimes data infrastructure that is as open as possible will benefit the organisations that maintain the data, in other cases it will not. To benefit everyone, it will be necessary for governments to provide support for some components.

5. Think big but start small: Do not start big. Start with the problems that are making it hard for people to make decisions or build new services, be agile and learn from experiments. Concrete and tar do not go out of date as quickly as data technologies do.

6. Design to adapt: Expect needs to change and expect other needs to vary between different stakeholders and local contexts. Be prepared to experiment with new technologies and ideas, look for desired paths, measure impact, learn from what works and what does not. Any part of data infrastructure might start as a small experiment but turn out to create significant impact and have high demand. If it is designed to adapt using approaches like human-centred design, by encouraging innovation and by using flexible modular approaches, this is most likely to happen.

7. Encourage open innovation: The best ideas can come from anywhere: individual citizens, large or small organisations and from the public, private or third sectors. Strong data infrastructure and open innovation will encourage and stimulate fair and equitable markets and innovative ways to both maintain data and use it to create new services.

3.3 Other guiding principles to consider

The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI) [13]: published in 2020, focus on promoting open scholarly infrastructure, advocating for the development of tools, platforms, and practices that foster open and collaborative research. They seek to address the challenges faced by researchers, institutions, and communities

in accessing, sharing, and disseminating knowledge. The principles highlight the importance of open access, data sharing, and transparency in scholarly communication. They also encourage the adoption of open-source software, standards, and interoperability to ensure a more inclusive and sustainable scholarly ecosystem.

FAIR Data Principles [70]: Published in 2016, this document outlines a set of principles designed to improve the infrastructure supporting the reuse of scholarly data. The principles were jointly endorsed by a diverse set of stakeholders, including academia, industry, funding agencies, and scholarly publishers. The goal is to enhance the reusability of data holdings by providing a concise and measurable set of guidelines. The FAIR Data Principles put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals. They describe distinct considerations for contemporary data publishing environments with respect to supporting both manual and automated deposition, exploration, sharing, and reuse. The principles are domain-independent and can be applied to a wide range of scholarly outputs. They cover four key areas: Findability (making data easy to find), Accessibility (making data easy to access), Interoperability (making data easy to integrate with other datasets), and Reusability (making data easy to reuse). Overall, the FAIR Data Principles provide a framework for improving the quality and accessibility of scholarly data. By following these principles, researchers can ensure that their data is easily discoverable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable by both humans and machines.

Ten Principles of Citizen Science [14]: published by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) in 2015, these principles guide the collaborative involvement of the public in scientific research. They emphasise open participation, scientific legitimacy, purposeful design, inclusivity and diversity, scientific learning, participant benefits, data quality, ethical considerations, open access, and long-term sustainability. These principles ensure that citizen science projects are inclusive, scientifically rigorous, and beneficial to both participants and the advancement of scientific knowledge, while upholding ethical standards and promoting transparency and accessibility.

4. Co-design of data services and infrastructures

The present report seeks to encourage the use of collaborative strategies such as co-design and co-development within the training of digital skills for the construction of data infrastructures and data services in citizen science. These strategies put the participation of end-users at the centre, opening different phases of their process to co-create the service or infrastructure.

Co-design is a creative process that allows a broad range of individuals to meaningfully contribute to the conceptualisation and resolution of an issue. Due to the fundamental shift in the conventional designer-client relationship, co-design enables the creation of added value together. By fostering and developing equitable collaboration between all the parties working to address a specific situation, it goes beyond consultation. Users are seen as 'experts' of their own experience throughout a co-design process, and their demands and concerns are given top priority during the creation of the final product [1].

Co-development in the context of this report refers to a collaborative approach where multiple individuals or organisations work together to develop software products or systems. It involves joint efforts, shared responsibilities, and effective coordination among the various contributors throughout the development lifecycle.

The Cos4Cloud case study is presented below as reference for the implementation of co-design in the development of data services and data infrastructures.

Key resource: The Co-design as a service: Methodological guide [1] published in 2023 provides a set of concepts and tools to implement co-design from conceptualisation to release of a service or infrastructure.

4.1 Cos4Cloud: Co-design of technological services for citizen science

The Cos4Cloud project¹, implemented from 2019 to 2023, was an EU-funded project under grant agreement No. 863463 aimed at advancing citizen science by developing 13 technological services. As part of this project, Cos4Cloud actively contributed to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), a major initiative focused on creating a federated infrastructure to facilitate open and seamless access to research data and services across Europe. By publishing a range of technological services for the citizen science community, Cos4Cloud not only fostered collaboration and data sharing but also integrated citizen science into the broader scientific landscape [15]. This section highlights the successful co-design of data services and infrastructure for citizen science within the framework of the Cos4Cloud project, aligning with the objectives and vision of the EOSC initiative.

Co-design is an approach that enables a wide range of people to contribute to problem formulation and solution in a creative manner. The co-design process places users at the centre, considering them as experts of their own experience and incorporating their needs and concerns into the design process [1]. The co-design process within the Cos4Cloud project follows a structured approach consisting of six phases (Figure 1). The first phase involves identifying the contextual challenges and issues specific to the project. Next, the technology mapping phase assesses the feasibility of different technologies and considers existing services and their limitations. Stakeholder mapping is then conducted to identify key stakeholders and address their motivations, risks, and recruitment strategies. The needs of users and the technological requirements are framed in the fourth phase. The service development phase combines co-design and agile methodologies to develop the services. The deployment and testing phase collects feedback from end-users to improve and validate the service. Finally, the co-design process culminates in the creation of a final service that is co-designed to meet the identified needs [69].

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/863463> / <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>

Fig. 3. Cos4Cloud co-design framework. The framework consists of seven phases that start from identifying the needs and requirements from a range of stakeholders and end users to a loop validation of the services using agile methodologies. The final deployment and testing are also a participatory process.

Methodological development

For implementing the framework, the Cos4Cloud project developed specific co-design session methodologies based on the needs and challenges identified by service leaders. One of the methodologies implemented is the Wheels Workshop Methodology, consisting of two parts: the First Impression Wheel and the Desirability Wheel. The First Impression Wheel includes questions related to service expectations, feasibility, direction, inputs, and potential risks. The Desirability Wheel focuses on desirability testing and content inventory.

A second methodology was the User Stories Workshop Methodology. This methodology aims to provide more actionable output suitable for service leaders making specific choices regarding user experience and workflows. The methodology includes tasks that address problems or challenges, aiming to identify why end users are interested in the service. The goals are to determine participants' service requirements and gather user stories to understand what each future end-user wants and why. It consists of two parts: user profile and user stories. The user profile part involves participants choosing an avatar, building their user profile, and discussing the main challenges they face when using citizen science apps. The User Stories part focuses on constructing user stories using predefined connectors and templates. The stories are standardised, well-defined, and actionable units of information following the "As a ..., I want/need to ..., so that/in order to ..." structure. These user stories serve as building blocks for functional descriptions in agile software development methodologies and facilitate integration with the Agile Prototype Methodology.

Example: MOBIS

Fig. 4. The Wheels Workshop Methodology, consisting of two parts: the First Impression Wheel and the Desirability Wheel. The First Impression Wheel includes questions related to service expectations, feasibility, direction, inputs, and potential risks. The Desirability Wheel focuses on desirability testing and content inventory [1].

Example:
FASTCAT-Cloud and FASTCAT-Edge

Fig. 5. The User Stories Workshop Methodology generates actionable insights by creating user profiles and constructing standardised user stories for agile software development. It focuses on user experience, workflows, and understanding user requirements and motivations [1].

The agile methodology plays a significant role in the co-design process within the Cos4Cloud project. The agile approach emphasises iterative and incremental development, allowing for flexibility and adaptation to changing requirements and circumstances. To ensure integration between the co-design workshops and the agile development teams, the concept of co-design digests was introduced. These digests serve as bridges between the outputs of the workshops and the concrete tasks and user stories for the development teams. They provide processed and analysed outcomes, including highlights, findings (both positive and negative), and reasoned user stories. The digests demonstrate how feedback from co-design sessions is incorporated into the development process of each service.

Communication and engagement strategy

An engagement strategy was created to build a co-design community that actively participates in the workshops. A target audience was defined based on the needs of each service and communication materials were established. Also, social networks were used to reach out to potential participants. Additionally, the communications team created informative materials such as infographics, video interviews, and mock-ups/prototypes of the services to provide participants with a better understanding of the offerings. After each co-design session, the communication team carried out several actions to maintain and grow the community. They conducted post-event surveys to gather feedback from internal evaluators, service developers, and participants. A summary of key points from each event was published as news on the project's website. The website also featured a 'Co-design highlights' section to showcase the positive inputs from participants and promote community engagement.

The co-design implementation in the Cos4Cloud project encompasses the development of methodologies, community engagement strategies, communication tactics, and methodological advancements. Cos4Cloud shows that putting the users at the centre of the development of the services and maintaining constant communication with them is a challenging but ultimately fruitful experience that opens up new approaches to the development of citizen science technologies.

5. Literature review methodology

The compilation of proven practices listed in section six stems from a meticulous literature review. Subsequently, the following paragraphs outline the steps taken, criteria established, and selected sources of information that were utilised to generate a comprehensive overview of the best practices within the context of collaborative design of data infrastructures and data services.

The review used two academic databases, Scopus, and Web of Science, to collect relevant literature. Also, it included Zenodo as one of the main repositories for open scientific literature in Europe, that incorporates grey literature and other kinds of documents such as policy briefs. Finally, an additional set of documents referenced by the authors and contributors were part of the final list of documents to review. A comprehensive search strategy was devised, incorporating specific keywords, listed in Table 1, related to collaborative design, data infrastructures, and data services. The chosen period for the study encompassed the past six years to ensure the inclusion of recent and up-to-date research. The primary objective was to gather articles and conference proceedings that contribute to the understanding of collaborative design in the context of data infrastructures and data services.

To carry out the literature review, the researchers employed a rigorous selection process. Initially, an extensive keyword search was performed across the databases, resulting in a pool of 192 potentially relevant articles, conference proceedings, reviews, and other documents (Table 2). Next, a systematic screening process was implemented, where the researchers assessed the titles and abstracts of the identified publications to determine their relevance to the research topic. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were established to ensure that only studies pertaining to collaborative design in the context of data infrastructures and data services were considered. Finally, a set of 65 documents was selected.

Table 1. Comparative database search for research analysis. Search strings used in three databases, Scopus, Web of Science, and Zenodo, for conducting research analysis. The table highlights the specific search queries employed in each database, including the criteria as keywords used, document types and timespan.

Scopus	Web of Science (WoS)
(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("citize* scien*" OR " participat* scien*" OR "crowd* scien*" OR " communit* scienc*" OR "volunteer* scien*" OR "volunteer* monitor*" OR "public* participat* scien*" OR "civic* scien*" OR "community-based monitor*" OR "	TOPIC: ("best practice*" OR " best practices*") ("data infrastructure" OR "data management" OR "data services" OR "data lifecycle" OR "research infrastructure") AND TOPIC: KEY ("citize* scien*" OR " participat* scien*" OR "crowd* scien*" OR "

participant* monitor*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("data infrastructure" OR "data management" OR "data services" OR "data lifecycle" OR "research infrastructure")) AND PUBYEAR > 2016 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "re")

communit* scienc*" OR "volunteer* scien*" OR "volunteer* monitor*" OR "public* participat* scien*" OR "civic* scien*" OR "community-based monitor*" OR " participant* monitor*") Refined by: DOCUMENT TYPES: (ARTICLE OR PROCEEDINGS PAPER OR REVIEW) RANGE: 2017-01-01 to 2023-12-31 LANGUAGE: english/spanish. Indexes: SCI- EXPANDED, SSCI, A & HCI, CSPCI-S, CSPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC

Zenodo

Queries: "citizen science" AND "best practices" AND data | "citizen science" AND "best practices" | "citizen science" AND "data infrastructure" | "citizen science" AND "open source" >> Access Right: Open >> File Type: pdf, html, docx >> Type: publication

To review the collection of 192 documents and identify if they comply with the specified criteria, the following three key criteria were defined:

1. The documents must be developed or proven within the context of citizen science and/or open science and/or the open-source movement. This criterion ensures that the research aligns with principles of inclusivity, collaboration, and transparency in scientific endeavours.
2. The documents should be applied in the field of information and communication technology (ICT), data management, data infrastructures, or data science. This criterion ensures relevance to the domain of technology-driven data practices.
3. The documents must explicitly or implicitly mention the documentation of best or proven practices. This criterion ensures that the documents provide insights into established methodologies or guidelines, facilitating the adoption of successful approaches within the research community.

Table 2. Results of the search conducted in databases and repositories. Results of the search conducted across Scopus, Web of Science, Zenodo, and documents referenced by authors. The initial search yielded a total of 257 documents, including duplicate entries. The duplicates were removed using the title field narrowed down to 192. After applying the 'selection criteria' to filter based on the title, abstract, and keywords, the collection was refined to 65 documents.

Source	Collection of documents to filter	Documents selected
Scopus	114	31
Web of Science	79	6
Zenodo	64	16
Referenced by authors	12	12

Total inc. duplicates	257	65
Final	192	65

After the final selection of 65 papers, a thorough analysis was conducted to extract key information and insights. Data extraction focused on three main components defined: guidelines, proven practices and lessons learned. This systematic approach aimed to extract valuable knowledge and actionable recommendations from the literature.

The following definitions were adopted for classifying the information extracted in the documents:

Best practice or proven practice (What works): is relative to available solutions and practices at a given time and that it will inevitably change over time [3]. Proven practices are methods that have been demonstrated to be effective and lend themselves to replication to other groups, organisations, and contexts. Typically referred to as 'best practices', they are sometimes called 'good practices'. The problem with the term 'best practice' is that it connotes that an ideal has been achieved, where 'proven practice' more reasonably asserts that an approach has been tried successfully. It is better to learn about and adapt proven practices that fit your environment, whether or not they are the 'best' [16].

Lessons learned (What didn't work): in the context of this report, lessons learned refer to valuable insights gained from experiences that did not work as expected. These insights are derived from documentation, presentations, discussions, and recordings, capturing what was attempted, what succeeded, what failed, problem-solving approaches, lessons for improvement, and key insights [7]. While the initial focus of this report is on documenting proven practices or best practices, it is essential to recognise the significance of documenting what did not work. This emphasis reflects the value placed by the citizen science community on learning from all types of experiences. Therefore, for the purpose of this document, the scope of lessons learned has been tailored to facilitate reading and information classification, recognising that the term extends beyond the specific context of this report.

Key resources (Generally accepted): generally adopted practices, principles, or recommendations that provide directions, and frameworks on how to develop certain components of the data infrastructure. Those that are considered theoretical or practical references with extensive validation are consolidated in this section.

6. Proven practices, lessons learned and key resources

This section presents the compilation of the results obtained from the detailed extraction of proven practices and lessons learned from the selected 65 documents. The extracted information has been organised into seven distinct sections to provide a comprehensive overview. The first section, 'Data infrastructure' focuses on the recommended frameworks and architectures for efficient data management and storage. The second section, 'Data services' encompass technologies, and processes for efficient data management and utilisation. The third section, 'Data collection' highlights the best practices and methodologies for acquiring and curating data

effectively. The fourth section, 'Data standards' outlines the established protocols and formats for ensuring data consistency and interoperability. The fifth section, 'Data quality assurance' encompasses strategies and techniques to maintain and assess data integrity and accuracy. The sixth section, 'Data accessibility', addresses approaches to promote open access and data sharing. The seventh section, 'Data ownership, policy, and ethics', explores the legal and ethical considerations related to data governance and ownership.

By organising the extracted results into these seven sections, this compilation provides a comprehensive resource for researchers and practitioners in navigating the diverse aspects of data management, ensuring adherence to best practices, and addressing critical considerations within the field. Additionally, for each of the seven sections mentioned, a list of key resources has been included to further enhance and amplify knowledge on the respective topics. These resources encompass seminal research papers, authoritative guidelines, relevant books, reputable websites, and other scholarly sources that delve deeper into the specific aspects of data infrastructure, data services, data collection, data standards, data quality assurance, data accessibility, data ownership, policy and ethics, and data security.

6.1 Data infrastructure

Data infrastructure refers to the underlying framework and components necessary for the collection, storage, management, and dissemination of data in a structured and efficient manner. It encompasses the technological infrastructure, such as databases, storage systems, and networks, as well as the software applications, tools, and protocols that facilitate data processing and sharing. Data infrastructure provides the foundation for data-driven activities, enabling researchers, scientists, and organisations to access, analyse, and derive insights from vast amounts of data. It plays a crucial role in supporting open science and citizen science initiatives by ensuring the availability, integrity, and accessibility of data, fostering collaboration, and promoting responsible data practices.

Proven practices

- **Reusing:** Leveraging existing infrastructures/technologies, not create new ones [17]:
 - Creating and maintaining bespoke systems can present its own set of challenges [18].
 - Infrastructures should, whenever possible, benefit from approaches and technologies that are characteristic to mainstream IT instead of trying to invent their own silo approaches [19].
- **Need of collaboration among researchers from different disciplines** with diverse expertise to address technical challenges related to data product structure, storage, execution of workflows as well as approaching technical interoperability among research infrastructures [20].
- **Interoperability:** Developing interoperable platforms for sharing and receiving data [21].
- **Standardisation:** Using standards, data definitions for shared language and standardised digital formats [3], [19].
- Developing **incremental** novelties for sustainability approach, adapting to rapidly changing technologies [3], [19].
- **Simplicity:** Choose a simple model based on features, that can easily be transformed with ready

to use tools into more sophisticated data models [19].

- **Flexibility:** Data infrastructure should be adaptable to unique project requirements.
- **Reuse of platforms:** Programmes that adopt a ready-made platform to be able to reduce costs for data management while increasing the use of citizen science data [10], [21].
- Develop **long-term infrastructures** for data discovery and preservation [22].
- A **common data platform** could open up opportunities to integrate data from global sources leading to development of data products and applications that can help users understand transboundary problems at the neighbourhood scale [4].
- Being aware of **costs:**
 - Using open source software to reduce costs [21] increases the possibility of users that can implement and further develop the tools to their needs [23].
 - Eliminating the need for expensive computer hardware can improve cost efficiency [24].
 - Development and maintenance costs for apps can vary considerably. Data collection and management technology can be the largest portion of overall cost [25].
 - Include data deposit cost in project proposal budgets to ensure proper archiving and sustainability [26].

Lessons learned

- Avoid rigidly adhering to a **particular standard or technology** for development [19].
- **Risk of high costs of development:**
 - Developing a novel or modifying an existing platform is expensive and requires ongoing costs for maintenance and modifications [18], [21].
- **Risk of high costs of design:**
 - High cost of app design is a potential obstacle to innovation [27].
- **Fragmentation:**
 - Non-standardised data from mobile apps is sent to various non-interconnected databases, leading to fragmentation [27].
- **Lack of documentation:**
 - Poor documentation available on metadata and data management practices from many app developers [27] limits the use and reuse of software.

Key resources

- **Data interoperability: A practitioner's guide to joining up data in the development sector:** This document is a guide on data interoperability in the development sector. It provides an overview of how to join up data across the data lifecycle and value chain, and includes information on data management, governance, and interoperability. It also includes practical tips for implementing data interoperability

and an assessment framework that data managers can use to assess the degree to which their systems are interoperable².

- **European Data Spaces – Scientific Insights into Data Sharing and Utilisation at Scale:** the document is focused on data sharing and utilisation at scale in Europe. It provides scientific insights and recommendations for policymakers, data providers, and AI developers to improve data sharing practices and increase transparency and accountability in the use of data spaces³.

6.2 Data services

Data services refer to a range of offerings, technologies, and processes designed to support the efficient management, processing, and utilisation of data. These services encompass various aspects, including data integration, data storage, data processing, data analysis, data visualisation, data governance, and data security. Data services are essential for enabling organisations and individuals to leverage data effectively, ensuring data quality, accessibility, and reliability while facilitating seamless data sharing and collaboration.

Proven practices

Data added value and user-centred services:

- Data harmonisation and metadata standardisation to create data services is needed [20].
- Use open access licences that allow the interoperability and sharing of relevant data [20].
- Need of multiple data sources: Data products will usually need to be built from multiple sources, e.g. mixing data from various opportunistic counts, repeated surveys or from observations that were sampled with different protocols or at different spatial and temporal resolutions [20].
- Products and services outside the main platform can be monetised [4].
- Provide personalised data for end-users in return: Providing personalised data summaries periodically is a valuable incentive and recognition for volunteer contributions [24].
- Trusted data repositories: Managing data locally and responding personally to individual requests for data is common practice among the research community. Datasets should be made available in trusted repositories. A number of attributes make a data repository trusted by the research community of a particular discipline, and these repositories may pursue certification (e.g., <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>) [26], [28], [29]. Choosing repositories that provide a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for permanent and citable referencing is a desirable practice [29].
 - With or without formal certification, a repository must be secure, have stable funding support, and provide sufficient infrastructure and metadata to ensure understandability and usability of datasets. These repositories must also be affordable [26].
 - When multiple repositories serve similar disciplines, shared policies and standards will allow users of these repositories to combine datasets [26].
 - Develop long-term repositories for citizen science project data and provide support for such repositories in the long term [23].
 - Data storage: How long you should keep data is an important cost and consideration for

² <https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/handle/11329/1971>

³ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129900>

citizen science projects. Repositories may need appraisal methods for scientific importance due to increasing data volume [26].

Collaborative software development and knowledge exchange:

- Design data services based on a ‘good code’, a code that is easily modifiable, it is simple and easy to read and it is safe [30].
- Code development must also:
 - Focus on code readability [31].
 - Less is more: Write as few lines as possible [31].
 - Include comments: Comments are explanatory lines in the computer code that allow you to understand the meaning of these lines. They will help the programmer to quickly understand someone else's code if it is necessary to change something in the program. Comments should be short and meaningful [30]–[33].
 - Naming: Use appropriate naming conventions, ascribe a name to each variable that clearly describes its purpose and always assign unique variable names [31].
 - Avoid long lines: It is easier for humans to read blocks of lines that are horizontally short and vertically long [31].
 - Avoid deep nesting: Too many nesting levels make code harder to read and follow [31].
 - Use the DRY (Don't Repeat Yourself) principle: Automate repetitive tasks whenever necessary. The same piece of code should not be repeated in the script [31].
 - Don't use lengthy functions: Ideally, a single function should carry out a single task [31].
- Tests: In this practice, developers write automated test scripts to make sure a piece of software works as expected. Tests can check different things, from individual methods right up to complex requirements [30], [32]–[34]:
 - Testing first encourages smaller, more modular units of code, which generally means better code [34].
 - Create different tests [30]:
 - unit tests that check particular parts of software;
 - complex tests that check the whole system;
 - load tests that check how the product operates under load;
 - regression tests that check how a modified app operates, and so on.
 - Automate testing: Test-driven development practices and automated testing tools have matured, and development teams should include unit, regression, performance, and security testing as part of their agile estimates [32].
- Documentation: Document your decisions and discussions. They can serve you well in the future when trying to solve a similar problem. Create decision records, using online platforms like Jira and Slack, for example [33].
- Code Review and Pair Programming: Encourage your team to submit their codes under review or even pair them from time to time to push discussions [33].
- The rituals embedded in the project management system Scrum and Agile development, including commitments, standups, sprint reviews, and retrospectives are now proven practices to enable team collaboration and drive successful implementation. But to demonstrate agility

over a long time, developers must take on responsibilities and coding practices that enable longer-term support and extensibility of the code they develop [32].

- Communication and collaboration tools: Software development collaboration tools such as Jira, Slack, Zoom, and Asana are becoming essential to guarantee easy communication and collaborative work [33].
- Retrospectives: Set up regular meetings to reflect on what worked and what didn't. What was the impact on your organisation? To facilitate, share your metrics dashboards with everyone so they can analyse and bring questions to the table [35].
- Post Mortem: Document the team's reflection on what went wrong, how it could have been avoided, and how to improve for the future if the situation happens again.
- Symposiums: Set up an event with a regular cadence where developers or tech professionals can bring a problem they faced to discuss potential solutions [35].

Key resources

- **Co-design as a service: Methodological guide.** The guide compiles the methodology implemented in Cos4Cloud project that designs technological data services for citizen observatories ⁴.

6.3 Data collection

Data collection refers to the systematic process of gathering and managing data from diverse sources within a citizen science project. It involves establishing the necessary mechanisms, protocols, and tools to enable efficient and standardised data collection by participants. The infrastructure provides the necessary framework for organising data collection efforts, ensuring data quality, and facilitating data submission and storage. This includes the development of data collection protocols, the deployment of mobile applications or online platforms for data submission, and the establishment of data management systems. The infrastructure also encompasses data validation, curation, and integration processes to ensure the reliability and interoperability of collected data. By focusing on robust data collection practices, citizen science infrastructure enables the aggregation of large-scale, high-quality datasets contributed by participants, enhancing scientific research, and facilitating evidence-based decision-making in a collaborative and inclusive manner.

Proven practices

Adoption of platform/technologies:

- **Design** a simple user interface that is engaging and can be applied across a diverse group of users with varied skills [10], [25], [37] or assess **existing data collection platforms** for reuse to bring costs down [29].

⁴ https://zenodo.org/record/7472450#.Y_52Oa2ZOs-

- Utilise **new technologies** such as online data entry forms, smartphones, and anomaly-detection filters to enhance efficiency and reduce data-entry error risks [36].
- Implement data collection processes that are independent from Internet access—for example, by allowing mobile apps to be used offline to collect data, which can then be uploaded later when Internet connection is available [21].

Methods and protocols for data collection:

- Use well-designed and standardised data collection methods with rigorous data-entry protocols to ensure data integrity and quality [5].
- Explain the chosen protocol, the project's data use, and the impact of quality on end uses [37].
- Make assumptions explicit in metadata to prevent data misuse in the wrong context [4], [36], [38].

Validation and review of data:

- Validate public-collected data using various methods before, during, and after collection [38]–[40]:
 - community/peer consensus;
 - expert verification;
 - automated verification;
 - model-based verification [10].
- Regularly review and quality check data collection, including screening for suspect data, observer bias and variation, and monitoring performance [29], [36].
 - Constantly re-evaluate technology adopted to collect data [24].
 - Appoint data-entry coordinators to manage data entry, organise and document collected data, and screen for database errors [36].
 - Ensure completeness of data collection and disallow submission of incomplete content [5].
 - Ensure traceability by collecting information on content submission time, source, location, and content provider's name [5].
 - Provide feedback and rewards to volunteers for their participation [27], [38], [39].

Preservation: Ensure long-term data preservation by archiving with more than one copy, different media technologies, and preservation at different locations [17].

About data collection protocols:

- Make data collection protocols simple and intuitive without compromising quality [10], [42], [43].
- Standardise data collection protocols based on shared goals, as seen in the Yukon River Inter-Tribal Watershed Council example [21].
- Combine multiple sources of data [24].
- Hybrid data collection methods can be successful in certain contexts [44], [45].
- Consider calibration, and instrumentation needs [10], [46].

- Design data collection processes in advance and test them with a small focus group [10].
- Establish a sampling plan with spatial and temporal scales consistent with science goals [24], [29].
- Some practical recommendations [42]:
 - Ensure consistent data messages, formats, and filenames.
 - Shift from a presence-only protocol to a count-based protocol for better data quality.
 - Provide known locations for biodiversity species rather than relying on volunteer-selected locations.

About collectors:

- Provide proper **training** and instructions to participants for data collection [10], [24], [29], [37], [43], [44], [46], [48].
- Address **inequality in participation** of volunteers:
 - It is a small number of contributors who make a large share of the contributions. Most participants contributed only once and with little effort, leaving the top 10% of contributors responsible for almost 80% of total classifications. In addition, projects often face uneven coverage, with a higher number of volunteers in urban areas compared to remote areas, which can impact the scale and effectiveness of the project [38], [46].
- Provide a **channel or forum for participant input** and communication [37].
- Complement participant data with **recruited volunteer** data to avoid blanks [45].

Lessons learned

- Lack of **documentation** in the metadata can reduce data's usability [10], [43].
- **Need of reporting uncertainty**: Lack of 'do not know' or 'unsure' reporting options or fields can lead to false precision levels or recording of invalid values [37].
- **Lack of harmonisation in data available**:
 - Data collected over multiple decades by a set of people that is constantly changing creates challenges with handling high-variety big data from diverse sources [40].
 - Curating, harmonising, and repurposing long-term datasets is difficult and iterative. Statistical models may need tailoring to accommodate design and observation changes. Using a subset of sufficiently complete data might be necessary [40].
- Difficulty of **maintaining long-term** programmes and interactions when virtually all available funding is limited to two or three years. It is vital to plan data storage, sharing and duration [24], [29].
- Lack of **commitment** from volunteers in collecting field data can lead to gaps in the data across time and space [49].

Key resources

- **Data management guide for public participation in scientific research – DataONE:** The resource provides a step-by-step of the data management cycle applicable in a citizen science project⁵. It includes practices and specific tools.
- **Data management planning for citizen science:** This guidance note provides specific, practical advice to citizen science practitioners (specifically those involved in the planning, collecting, storing or using data) about the development of data management plans to support the value of datasets from citizen science projects⁶.

6.4 Data standards

Data standards refer to the established guidelines, protocols, and specifications that ensure the consistency, interoperability, and quality of collected data across different projects and initiatives. These standards define the formats, structures, and metadata requirements for data collection, management, and sharing. They encompass various aspects such as data formats, variable naming conventions, data documentation, and data quality control procedures. Data standards play a crucial role in facilitating data integration, comparability, and reusability, allowing data collected from multiple sources to be combined and analysed effectively. They promote data harmonisation and enhance the reliability and credibility of citizen science data, enabling researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders to trust and utilise the collected information for scientific research, decision-making, and policy formulation.

Proven practices

- Data should be **simple** [19], **uniform** [4] and **representative** (adequate representation and distribution of the target population or area) [37].
- **Normalisation:**
 - Align data models to national and global systems [25].
 - Standardise variables to existing ontologies [51].
 - Use known metadata standards for common data format, storage, description, and interoperability.
 - Use international standards such as ISO 19115 (Geographic information and services), ISO 19157 (Quality of geographic data), and ISO 8000 (Data quality) especially ISO 25012 (Data quality model) is recommended as a point of reference for quality control of citizen science projects [37].
 - Document the metadata extensively, this is helpful to communicate the ‘known quality’ of the data, while data reuse is enabled by extensive metadata descriptions of dataset purposes and methods of creation [37].

⁵ <https://dataoneorg.github.io/Education/bestpractices/>

⁶ <https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/handle/11329/1406>

- The use of metadata also supports FAIR data principles, ECSA Ten Principles of Citizen Science, and ECSA's Characteristics of Citizen Science [14].
- The standard created by the citizen science community, PPSR (Public Participation in Scientific Research) is one the promoted data standards for citizen science [29].
- The standard Darwin Core is currently adopted as the main data standard [19], [23], [44], [52] and Dublin Core [44], [53] for exchanging biodiversity data.
- Enable efficient **aggregation and exchange** of information [3]:
 - Tracing: Assign Persistent Identifier (PID) or DOI to the dataset [28].
 - Repository: Indicate if data is published on a general public repository, domain-specific repository, or website [28], [51].
 - Openness of data: Determine if data is accessible without authentication [28].
 - Vocabulary and ontology usage: Highlight the use of specific vocabularies or ontologies for describing data or metadata to enhance interoperability [28].
 - Licence type: Specify the type of licence used for the data [28].
 - Document: Include data standard operating procedures (SOP), track data processing steps [51].
 - Publish calibration details: Calibrate sensor response if one wishes to compare one sensor's data to that of another sensor or to nearby regulatory monitoring data [4].
- **Use of metadata:**
 - Develop controlled vocabularies for metadata documentation, particularly to enable fitness for purpose assessments [22].
 - Make metadata discoverable (structured descriptive information about datasets) available through data catalogues [22].
 - Show the metadata fields used to describe the data and any software references [28].
 - Include version control, and pre-processing of data [28].
 - Include details on formatting guidelines such as the date and time string format to the specific metadata [4].
 - Report confidence intervals along with measurements [4].
 - Data quality elements such as precision, bias, detection limit, age, and calibration can be embedded in the metadata [4].
- Avoid "good data" / "bad data" division: consider if data is "good enough" for the intended objective [4].

Lessons learned

- Do not impose unshared standards [3], [21].
- Lack of standards in metadata: It makes it difficult to harmonise data from different sources.
- ISO 19157's applicability presents some challenges for volunteered geographic information [54]:
 - Standard is not perfect due to differences between authoritative and volunteered

- geographic information.
- Volunteered geographic information is heterogeneous and lacks required specifications and reference data.
- Additional quality indicators, such as reliability, should be used to extend the standard.

Key resources

- **Public Participation in Scientific Research-Core (PPSR-Core) project:** PPSR Core is a set of global, transdisciplinary data and metadata standards for Public Participation in Scientific Research (citizen science). This standard includes: Project Metadata Model or (PMM), Dataset Metadata Model (DMM), and Observation Data Model (ODM)⁷.
- **Research data management challenges in citizen science projects and recommendations for library support services:** A scoping review and case study: A review and case study of Danish citizen science projects that makes recommendations for publication platforms and data standards applied by different projects⁸.

6.5 Data quality assurance

Data quality assurance refers to the systematic processes, procedures, and practices implemented to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and integrity of collected data. It involves various measures taken throughout the data lifecycle to identify and address potential sources of errors, biases, or inconsistencies that could impact data quality. Quality assurance activities may include robust data collection protocols, standardised methodologies, training and support for participants, data validation and verification procedures, and data quality control checks. These processes aim to minimise errors, enhance the reliability of data, and promote the credibility of citizen science projects. The implementation of effective data quality assurance practices allows citizen science initiatives to enhance the scientific value of collected data, enable data comparability and integration, and foster trust among the broader scientific community and stakeholders who rely on the data for decision-making, research, and policy formulation.

Proven practices

Training and Support:

- **Training Participants:** Providing enhanced and comprehensive training [5], [45], [55] enables participants to grasp the importance of data quality and recognise the minimum data quality standards essential for each citizen science project [29], [37].
- **Help sections and guides:**
 - Help must be available in case of any queries, such as how to report gathered data for

⁷ <https://core.citizenscience.org/>

⁸ <https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2021-025>

the scientific project (leveraging online forums, target groups, organising face-to-face meetings, regular teleconference calls) [38].

- Provide useful and understandable help sections and guides within software apps and websites used by the contributors [37].

Data Quality Assessment:

- **Quantification of uncertainty** or confidence intervals is essential for understanding and using sensor data. The interval should fully capture the uncertainty in the data and the width of this interval can help determine the usefulness of the data [4].
- How to **assess uncertainty**: Understand the data collectors' process to identify quality challenges, including the impact of uncertainty in contributions and how it can be captured or traced [37]. Estimate existing levels of accuracy or error within a dataset [37].
- **Statistical issues**: Incorporating large datasets brings advantages, but statistical issues multiply: collinearity, false positives, significant but tiny effects [40].
- **Determine explicitly desired data quality**: Define validity ranges at project planning and design stage: For example, is the accuracy of the location of an object within 100 m acceptable, is a plant identification to genus level useful, etc. [37] / Define desired data quality explicitly in terms of study objectives grounded in specific analyses or estimates [37] / Estimate a requisite level of accuracy or error within the raw data that allows study objectives to be achieved.
 - The construct of data quality means that data is of high enough quality to serve a project's goals: there are no universal criteria to establish quality in scientific data because it is inherently contextual [22], [29].

Validation and Verification:

- **Pre-testing**: Gathering sample data before a citizen science project begins using both expert and beginner contributors. This can help identify unforeseen sources of errors or other problems that can be fixed before the project starts [37].
- **Data Validation**: Professional processing and quality control of the data are advisable [24]. Citizen-generated data may need to be validated by national statistical offices (NSOs) before inclusion in official reporting [17].
 - Ways of data validation: peer verification, expert verification, automatic quality assessment, and model-based quality assessment [10], [37].
- **Cross-validating the Data**: Citizen science data may be analysed along with other scientific or instrumental observations [22]. Comparison with authoritative data improves the confidence and validity of collected data [37]. Use community consensus for data validation and cross-checking [29].
- **Triangulation**: Use multiple observers, methods, and data sources to overcome biases [29]. Triangulation can contribute to the reproducibility debate, as reproducing studies involves more than just replicating methods [40].

Addressing Bias:

- **Identifying sources of bias** helps design strategies to mitigate or manage them effectively. Some

biases identified in citizen science data are:

- Positive spatial bias: higher human population, better accessibility, Internet access.
- Offline reporting helps avoid spatial biases, ensuring remote areas are not under-reported [27].
- Positive temporal bias: more records during weekends, holidays, contests.
- Taxonomic bias: underrepresentation of rare, cryptic, or hard-to-identify species; overlooking common species; over-reporting sought-after species [10], [29], [48].
- Observer bias: individual perceptions and experience levels.
- Machine learning for flagging/eliminating false reports reduces verification time [27].
- Sensor bias: Citizen science projects often use low-cost sensors; the cost and limitations of these sensors can produce biases in the data collected [29].

Data and monitoring protocols:

- **On-the-fly data correction or cleansing tools:** Install tools to verify (and possibly reject) data and monitoring protocols [38]. Allow for auto-correction of some errors prior to reporting, for example, autocorrecting geocoding of address data, topology checks, and enforcing selection of an attribute value from a dictionary list [37], [38].
- **Reuse of successful data quality protocols:** There is little value in constantly reinventing protocols for similar problems being tackled by other citizen science groups or projects [37].

Metadata, Documentation, and Controlled Vocabularies:

- **Comprehensive metadata:** should describe the quality aspects of the data as comprehensively as possible, including its provenance, treatment, constraints, and biases, in a structured, standardised way [22].
- **Develop controlled vocabularies:** for articulating common data-quality practices that can be included in metadata for datasets and/or observations [22].
- **Documentation and protocols:** is also needed to describe exactly how the data were collected, including information on specific protocols [17], [38] / Appropriate documentation and metadata are the most effective and appropriate deterrents against using data for unsuitable purposes [37].

Quality control and assurance:

- **Peer review:** or quality control for data in repositories. Many repositories do not offer peer review but provide curation. Peer review can ensure metadata, methodology, and data processing align with FAIR principles. Components for a quality peer review of a dataset include: clear metadata, descriptions, and limitations, lab work methods or instruments, QA/QC for instrument calibration, presence and circumstances of survey data, identification of raw or processed data status and citations for source data and algorithms used [26].
- **Quality control practices:** Citizen science practitioners should document their QA/QC practices on project websites and/or through formal QA/QC plans [22]. / Record and communicate quality assurance practices [29], [37] / Communicating data quality practices can help citizen science collaboration by identifying shared issues and concerns [37] and increases trust and reusability

[56]. / Quality assurance (QA) processes should be implemented before and during data collection [29]. They can be implemented at the design stage by integrating quality characteristics into a platform's design [5], [37].

Data management and compatibility:

- **Recursive monitoring:** keeps track of data quality over time and generates reports on uncertainties and variations [37]
 - Focus on data model and user interface improvements.
 - Data quality characteristics act as constraints during the design stage.
 - Integration into a new platform is easier compared to existing platforms.
 - Integrating into existing platforms may require shutting down or modifying current data.
 - User interface integration is easier and does not require significant changes to the data model.
- **Compatible information systems:** allow for long-term storage, curation, and archiving of data from citizen science projects. They ensure reproducibility and compatibility with standardised datasets [10], [37].
 - Avoid data redundancy: Matching or linking facilitates aligning or merging similar data records [37].
- **Training participants and providing feedback:** additional time devoted to training, or different training techniques, could potentially produce higher consistency levels [5], [29], [45].
 - The detection of inconsistent observers is a means to identify where additional training may be required [57].
 - Provide feedback: ongoing feedback on volunteer identifications, based on professional validation of their photographs, increases both volunteer accuracy and retention [42].
 - Facilitate identification using simple filters: provide guiding filters to untrained volunteers allows them to learn likely species identifications based on a target pattern (e.g. animal's morphological traits) [42].
 - Scientists can verify the abilities of participants by asking them to classify objects that have been previously classified by experts [41].
 - Testing participants can help identify where gaps might exist that can be addressed through training. Some specific examples are listed below:
 - eBird assists its volunteers with dynamically generated data-entry forms that list the most common birds for a volunteer's given location and time, increasing both volunteer awareness of the local species and data quality [42].
 - Stardust@home uses known "seeded" images for ongoing assessment and provides feedback to volunteers on their success rate so that they may voluntarily try to improve their accuracy [42].
 - Injecting professionally classified (e.g. Stardust@home) or artificially generated (e.g. Planet Hunters) vouchers into voucher sets given to volunteers for classification in order to evaluate ongoing volunteer performance [42].
 - The observation skill of eBird users was assessed using species accumulation

curves, and when skill was incorporated into bird species distribution models, model accuracy increased for approximately 90% of the 120 species tested [42].

- Cross validation and expert review:
 - Use paid interns to monitor a random sample, in addition to the volunteer-generated sample, to investigate sampling bias and observation errors [45].
 - Comparison of participant-gathered data with a reference group or experts [10], [29], [55].
 - Data from other sources serves as a source of verification [49].
 - Expert validation of volunteer classifications has been shown to be more cost-effective than direct expert classification for lady beetles [42].
 - Expert review: Project FeederWatch uses a “smart filter” system that flags observations of unlikely species and unusually large numbers of birds. Flagged data are immediately sent to regional experts who then ask for photographic vouchers and supporting details from volunteers to validate the sightings [42].
 - Snapshot Serengeti uses a suite of post-hoc statistical metrics to identify “difficult” images of African animals to be sent for expert review [42].
 - Validate data input (e.g. syntax, format and values) by checking compliance against schemas [49].
 - Implement a metadata and data suggestion/validation process that employs XML schemas and controlled vocabularies to restrict input to permitted values/ranges and to validate the data [49].
 - CoralWatch: The data is assigned a rating value based on the outcome of the quality measure process. If the data does not pass the data quality assessment, it will be marked ‘unvalidated’ [49].
- Inclusiveness: is important not only for social justice reasons, but also from the scientific standpoint to ensure a representative dataset [29].
- Reputation algorithms: Consider the user’s reputation and trustworthiness to assess the reliability and quality of the data [5], [29], [47]. Poor trust metrics associated with individual volunteers could be used to target online training modules. Good trust metrics could be used to reward, encourage and retain volunteers [49]. Trust metrics can be used for querying, filtering and reporting services [49]. Estimates of observer skill or reliability can be calculated [37].
- Improving Data Quality:
 - Using workflows, processes, and user centred design to minimise the risk of user errors and ensure that consistent data formats and mandatory attributes are recorded correctly, along with consistent use of vocabularies, spatial referencing, and dates [22].
 - Assuming that standards and best practices already exist, providers should codify them into their software to ensure consistency and offer guidance for users [10], [22].
 - A dedicated website fosters social networks. Participants can comment on other’s observations and this helps promote scientific learning, data quality, and community building [29].
 - Use of IT platforms has been helpful in codifying and enforcing rules. This has led to

- improved quality, reliability, reusability, and has enhanced scientific trustworthiness [3].
- Using cell phones when recording data is having a large impact, reducing chances that data will not be shared or that errors will creep in before data is shared [41].
- Check for errors as early in the process as possible [41]:
 - (1) requiring users to choose from pick lists rather than using free form input fields,
 - (2) using electronic input via mobile devices,
 - (3) checking input immediately from users to give feedback if values seem questionable given the context of the situation,
 - (4) taking input such as time and location from sensors when possible, etc.

Lessons learned

Data Quality and Reliability in Citizen Science:

- Key functionalities for reporting, validating data and automating quality control are often absent from apps [25], [27].
- Difficulties of locating information about data quality methods from project web sites [41].
- Causes of the majority of errors in data:
 - lack of validation and consistency checking;
 - lack of automated metadata/data extraction;
 - lack of user authentication and automatic attribution of data to individuals;
 - absence of a precisely defined and extensible data model and corresponding schema;
 - lack of data quality assessment measures;
 - lack of feedback to volunteers on their data; and
 - lack of graphing, trend analysis and visualisation tools that enable errors or missing data to be easily detected [48], [49].
- Data quality problems can arise in citizen science projects due to [37]:
 - Data collection protocols not being followed by participants.
 - Data collection protocols not matching the goals of the project or the probable participants.
 - Data collection protocols being incorrectly implemented.
 - Data collection protocols not being comprehensive and being used by stakeholders with different data quality expectation levels.
 - Data used not being fit for purpose.
 - Poorly designed or overly complex protocols can also create skill inequality if some protocols assume a specific level of scientific training before they can be used.
 - When datasets are not adequately described with relevant metadata, their potential for secondary uses is significantly compromised, frequently resulting in whole datasets being discounted as untrustworthy and reinforcing the perceptions of poor rigour in citizen science [10], [22].

- Most types of bias found in citizen-science datasets are also found in professionally produced datasets and can be mitigated using existing statistical tools [37].
- Researchers typically consider data quality and fitness for use in individual project design, explaining the factors affecting data quality within the text of research papers. However, such explanations are not always documented in metadata accompanying the primary raw and processed datasets used in the research, and if they are documented, it is rarely in structured, standardised formats. These cases both create a number of significant problems and constraints for secondary uses of the primary data [22].

Reputation and Comparing Data in Citizen Science:

- Reputation to assess reliability:
 - It does not necessarily mean that the information given by the most trustworthy person is always the best [47].
 - The system needs an initial reputation model to be accurate and this initial model is based on registration information of the user, which can lead to privacy issues [47].
- Compare data: If multiple participants gathered data on the same location from different viewpoints, the measurement results could be compared against each other and corrected appropriately [47].

Ethical Considerations in Gamification of Citizen Science [10]:

- Gamification can enhance participation but may demotivate non-competitive participants.
- Potential distraction from scientific data collection.
- Risk of unfair practices and conflict with open data principles.
- Potential for inequity due to varying skills and resources.
- Consider game design, participant strategies, values, motivations, and acknowledgment outside gaming context.

Key resources

- **Still in need of norms:** The state of the data in citizen science: The paper samples 36 projects from English-speaking countries. It presents recommendations for the citizen science community related to data quality, data infrastructure, data governance, data documentation, and data access⁹.
- **Data Quality in Citizen Science:** Review of citizen science projects, analysing needs in dataset standards and usage of international standards (ISO)¹⁰.

⁹ <https://theoryandpractice.citizenscienceassociation.org/articles/10.5334/cstp.303>

¹⁰ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_8

6.6 Data accessibility

Data accessibility refers to the availability and ease of accessing and retrieving collected data by a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and the general public. It involves ensuring that data collected within citizen science projects are made openly accessible and usable, following principles of openness, transparency, and inclusivity. Data accessibility measures may include providing data through online platforms, data repositories, or APIs, accompanied by clear metadata and documentation. Efforts are made to ensure data are presented in a standardised and user-friendly format, allowing individuals to search, download, and analyse the data effectively. Promoting data accessibility in citizen science projects enables wider participation, encourages collaboration, and facilitates the reuse of data for various purposes, such as scientific research, policy-making, and education.

Proven practices

Data Accessibility and Repositories in Citizen Science:

- Integration of the software code in open access publications: An increasing number of journals are providing open access publication options or journals specifically focused on making data and/or software discoverable, accessible and citable [25], [53]. As a notable example in the geospatial domain, the AGILE (Association of Geographic Information Laboratories in Europe) has recently published the Reproducible Paper Guidelines [59], which require the presence of a section on data and software availability in all papers submitted to the AGILE conferences and details its requirements [19], [26], [28].
- Publishing the data corresponding to an academic publication (i.e., a data paper) is a practical idea that has the potential to promote data sharing, and this has several benefits for researchers. Here, a data paper should include all available data, not just the data used in the original article [52].
- Moving from data sharing (i.e. providing access under specified circumstances) to data publication with the possibility to get cited which may be a motivation to make data open access [23]. Open data publication maximises the use of the data in policy processes and provides better return to citizen scientists on their contribution and value of their data [39].

Data harmonisation and reuse:

- Diversity in data formats: datasets might be available in multiple serialisations that may differ in various ways, including natural language, media-type or format, schematic organisation, temporal and spatial resolution, level of detail or profiles [19].
- Data availability and interest: Harmonising and making data available that is of little interest to users, while not focusing on those datasets that are highly desired makes little sense [19].
- Smart templates: Use smart templates for integrating and harmonising data from different sources [26], [29].
- Ease of data use: There should be a relatively easy way to use the collected data to get more benefits from the citizen science project [47].
- Clear links between external repositories and project web presence and vice versa [28].

Data Interoperability, Metadata, and Standards in Citizen Science:

- Promote data reusability and interoperability: ensure that datasets are made available and are easily re-usable together with other sources with as little prior knowledge as possible [10], [26], [39].
- Data efficiency: duplication of data between different sources should ideally be avoided [39]. FAIR Principles: Making data findable is important so that researchers and people using citizen science data can find overlaps in things that they are studying. This makes it so that repetition does not occur, and people are using existing resources in the best way possible [28], [43].
- Well-documented APIs can play a central role for coupling the different data spaces in a loose and flexible manner [19]. APIs also play a central role in accessibility [43].
- A common practice in dataset development is to include only data and metadata that are useful for their own project, without considering if other data would be useful for others. An appropriate best practice is to adhere to “minimal dataset” standards. A minimal dataset is one that includes at least the minimum amount of data and metadata to ensure consistency, utility, and interoperability with other datasets [26].
- Describing data with rich metadata and using metadata that follow specific standards or community-recognised ontologies is important for securing interoperability [23], [28], [48], [51].
- Data dictionaries and standards are essential for interpretation and analysis by other researchers. Acceptable data formats and dictionaries can be defined by funding agencies, standard-making bodies, or repositories. Clear descriptions of data dictionaries/standards should be in metadata workflow descriptions. Policies are needed to manage inconsistencies in data dictionaries for long-term curation [26], [28].
- The use of persistent identifiers (e.g., Digital Object Identifiers [DOIs]) can ensure that researchers are able to refer to a unique dataset produced at a given point in time by providing persistent URLs to data that are retained even if, for example, data moves from a project website to a longer-term repository. This is important for traceability in scientific findings as well as for appropriate attribution [22].
- Linking good data management practices to already-articulated community values like transparency [22].
- Easy access to data in standardised formats and multiple download options such as raw and cleaned data [17]:
 - temporal and spatial subsets, and
 - format options such as spreadsheets, geographic formats, and API access
 - The ability to subset the data is particularly beneficial in regions with limited bandwidth.
- The keys of the data records must be non-empty, and the formats must be machine readable. There is also a need for consistency of structure of datasets between different time periods [60].

Data citation:

- The Research Data Alliance (RDA) Data Citation working group has developed a recommendation based on two principles: first, one must ensure that data are stored in a versioned and timestamped manner; second, the persistent identifier (PID) to the citable data

should comprise a query to the dataset and a timestamp. Researchers found the principles highly applicable to a test citizen science dataset [23].

- GBIF use of DOI: As one example, GBIF, together with its partners and members, implemented DOI minting and tracking mechanisms to link publications citing data sources with the original source data, which include datasets sourced from citizen science projects [22].

Lessons learned

Data management planning in citizen science projects:

- Lack of data management planning: Many citizen science projects are relatively small scale and probably lack experience and/or access to tools for data management planning [39]. An analysis of citizen science projects found that over 50% of all projects had no data management plan in place, causing subsequent difficulties throughout the data analysis process. Projects should complete a full data management plan – however provisional – as early as possible, which should be updated or replaced as necessary throughout the lifetime of the project [28], [61].

Data accessibility and sharing challenges:

- Limited open data repositories usage: Although some projects deposit their data on national or institutional repositories, less than one third make them freely available on an open data repository, e.g., through GBIF publication [39]. This lack of use of public repositories was associated with a number of significant outcomes for the usability of the data such as outdated URLs, missing versioning of metadata and datasets, unavailability of machine readable licensing, lack of specification for conditions for reuse of data, missing specifications for the hardware and software used to generate the data, and lack of ontology or specified vocabulary to describe how the data or fields relate to one another [28], [48].
- Research data should not be archived in proprietary formats. For proprietary platform-dependent data, provide non-proprietary formats or software for approximation [26].
- Citizen science data accessibility: a research in 2017 analysed species monitoring datasets within GBIF, finding that while citizen science datasets made up the majority of the data sources, they were significantly less openly accessible than commercial datasets and those provided by research institutions [28].
- Requiring registration for access to data can help to track usage, but may serve as an impediment for some users [22].

Data sharing attitudes and incentives:

- Reluctance to share data: academic researchers may be reluctant to share data before they have published their findings [23]:
 - Traditional attitudes: Traditionally, many ecologists have subscribed to the idea that data should be collected, managed, and accessed only by the collector. As a result,

ecological data other than those used for publication have remained unused [26], [52].

- Positive incentives: positive incentives (citations, awards, credit) are desirable for encouraging public access to datasets. In addition, publishers can require community standards and public accessibility of datasets after publication. They can also require researchers to cite all data sources that are used. CrossRef and Scholix make it easier to track the use of data and give it more value [26].

Access to data collected by citizens:

- Ethics and FAIR Data: It is unethical for data that is collected by citizens to remain closed and inaccessible to the public [51], [58]. Many datasets that researchers produce do not apply FAIR principles and are often siloed from one another [51]. It is vital that the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data principles be applied where possible. Where data is being made open, the correct licensing scheme must be specified; otherwise, such data cannot be used [28], [46], [48].

Overcoming barriers to data sharing and preservation:

- Lack of incentives: Incentives are often missing for researchers to invest the time and effort required to make their data open or FAIR, since data cleaning and documentation are time-consuming activities that lack the same incentives as, for example, publication [22], [28].
 - There is a lack of accountability by outside researchers in returning data to the community in a useful format [21].
 - It is also a challenge to encourage industry actors to share industry collected environmental data. For example, commercial fisheries and environmental impact assessment are restricted due to commercial-in-confidence clauses [18].
 - Larger projects share data due to political pressures; smaller projects are not subject to the same expectations [28].
- Lack of long-term data preservation: While not all data need to be archived, at present probably too little is being proactively preserved for the long term [22]. / There are still no appropriate solutions for some requirements, for example for the long-term accessibility of a database [10], [62].
- The interoperability of community science data from mobile apps and transparency by app developers as to how and where data are stored are high priorities for the field [27], [28].

Key resource

- **Guide to Data Charter for Citizen Science:** the guide provides a set of principles to support open and interoperable citizen-science data. The document outlines a series of steps that citizen-science projects can take to make their data more accessible and reusable, including offering data in a structured and machine-readable format, using open data formats, and providing unique identifiers for observations.¹¹

¹¹ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/data-charter-and-guide-citizen-science>

6.7 Data ownership, policy, and ethics

Data ownership, policy, and ethics in citizen science involve addressing the rights, responsibilities, and considerations associated with the data collected within the context of citizen science projects. It encompasses defining and clarifying who owns the data, establishing policies and guidelines for data usage, sharing, and storage, and ensuring ethical considerations are upheld throughout the data lifecycle. Data ownership may be attributed to the individuals or organisations responsible for initiating and coordinating the citizen science project, while respecting the contributions of participants who collect the data. Policies and guidelines are developed to outline data access, intellectual property rights, data sharing agreements, and data privacy protection. Ethical considerations include obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring confidentiality, safeguarding privacy, and adhering to ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects. Additionally, data ownership, policy, and ethics in citizen science involve promoting responsible data practices, encouraging data transparency, and addressing any potential biases or conflicts of interest. The consideration of these aspects in citizen science projects can foster trust, accountability, and social responsibility while promoting the responsible and ethical use of data for the benefit of scientific research and society as a whole.

Proven practices

Data policy:

- Clear information: Explicit information on data policy and governance (regarding personal and research data) must be published within the project, and participants must consent to this information prior to participation [5], [10], [23].
- Clear data management policies and agreements on how data is handled among the participants (collectors, researchers, managers) are necessary to secure the data [23].
- Data sharing policy: Develop a data sharing policy that clearly states any restriction on data sharing; consider impacts on resource security and volunteer privacy in determining restrictions, and plan for what to do if a difficult scenario should arise (i.e. detection of illegal activity) [10], [23], [48], [51]. Define policies on data use by outside parties and restrictions on personal data sharing [58].
- Standard data policies: Citizen science practitioners should carefully consider trade-offs between openness and privacy. Researchers seeking to advance the field could develop standard data policies, including privacy policies and terms of use, that clearly outline data governance practices [10], [22].
- Indigenous data sovereignty: Growing recognition of Indigenous data sovereignty and development of frameworks and protocols for its implementation [21], [40], [63].
- Guiding values: Four common values that help guide digital data use in the non-profit sector: voluntary or permission-based participation, recognition of the privacy rights of individuals, a public benefit mission, a pluralistic effort to engage diverse participants [64].
- Compliance with regulations: Identify and comply with relevant laws and regulations [29], [58], [61]. Examples: EU General Data Protection Regulation and data minimization principle. Open Data Policy in the U.S. aims to improve public access while ensuring privacy protection. Belmont

- Report and other ethical codes outline best practices for research involving human subjects.
- Adherence to free, prior, and informed consent (FPIC): Adherence to FPIC and clear agreements on data ownership/use are needed to prevent potential misuse by private companies [63].
- Funding requirements: As a matter of policy, agencies providing funding should require that datasets need to be open [26].

Data privacy:

- Understandable terms: The constraints and rules concerning the use of digital data should be explained in terms understandable to everyone [38].
- Addressing tensions: During project development, identify potential tensions between data quality, privacy protection, resource security, transparency, and trust in consultation with stakeholders [23]. Develop a privacy policy or volunteer agreement that addresses these tensions and is consistent with existing guidelines [23].
- Data compromises: Determine which data points you can and cannot compromise on in terms of precision, public visibility, and data sharing; clearly state these decisions, and implement the supporting technologies (fuzzing locations, anonymizing identities, etc.) [23], [29], [48], [58], [65].
- Privacy risks: Citizen science programs are not often designed with privacy in mind. Non-discriminant collection can capture private information for example, unintended capture of identifiable images or conversations. This is potentially illegal in some jurisdictions [58].
 - Give ample notice of privacy choices. Explain the circumstances under which normal participation could be a risk to personal privacy. Inform volunteers who will review their data for quality control [23].
 - Give volunteers the option to hide certain data points and locations from public view or have data publicly visible but attributed anonymously [23]. Giving volunteers the possibility to stay anonymous is more important than their disclosure of conflicts of interest [23], [66].
 - Allow volunteers to delete and modify their data – both traditional personal information and submitted data that may contain information “about” the volunteer [23], [66].
- Data collection and management: Require only minimum personal data about volunteers. Demonstrate the value of the data you collect and explain who will be able to see it. Multilevel access control that considers different stakeholders’ roles and needs may be appropriate [23], [29]. Recommendations [5], [23], [48], [66]:
 - Collect as few personal and sensitive data as necessary.
 - Obfuscate such information upon publication or sharing.
 - Clearly inform the participants of what will be shared, why it is necessary and how it will be done.
- Iterative evaluation and feedback: Practise iterative evaluation of policies and practices in use to assess their impact on the ability to achieve program goals [23]. Develop a process for soliciting regular feedback from participants [23], [58].
 - Current findings indicate that restrictions associated with datasets are not clearly communicated to potential users or, in many cases, not communicated at all [28].
- Design strategies for notification and collection of data that consider the participant's risk when

sharing their exact location [47].

- Location sharing: Different options to share locations in iNaturalist: open, obscured, or private, with varying specificity. This choice supports privacy, with one key exception: Observations of threatened or endangered species are automatically “private” [66].
- Third-party privacy policies: Project managers must consider the personal information privacy policies of third-party technologies used for project management and communication [64]. These technologies can present additional risks for revealing volunteers, which may conflict with a citizen science project’s mission.

Data ownership, licensing, and intellectual property rights:

- Transparent Intellectual Property Rights (IPR): Allow sharing IPR, education or monetary value with volunteers [23].
- Credit originators: By giving credit via full citation to the originators of data, researchers can more appropriately acknowledge the contribution of the actual data [10], [52].
- Individual credit is an incentive for participants (e.g., co-authorship) [29].
- Standardised licensing framework: A standardised and simple licensing framework is therefore needed. Contemporary SDIs provide the legislative foundation for the standardisation of licences [19]. Clear data licensing helps enable open data by clarifying to third party users the status of a dataset and their ability to use the data for different purposes and under different conditions [22], [48].
- Citizen science projects should ensure that data ownership and data use rights are clearly stated and reflect the priorities of the volunteers. The adoption of open, machine-readable licences is recommended [17].
- Establish data ownership during design: Establish agreements regarding data sharing and ownership, communication of results, and publication during the study design phase [4].
- Use of Creative Commons Licences: If the licensing conditions for a dataset are unknown, or too difficult to understand, for example, due to a customised licence, users are very likely to avoid using the content and look for substitutes. That is why it is essential that well-established and easily understandable licences such as those from Creative Commons become the norm. Apart from choosing the right licences, a comprehensive licensing framework should be developed and implemented in practice [19].
 - Use of a standardised and well-known open data licence, such as the Creative Commons licences [52].
 - GBIF and JBIF already apply Creative Commons open data licences to almost all of the datasets [52].
 - Communicate licences: Communicate information about licences to stakeholders and participants [10].
- Need for regulation: Regulatory aspects that would ensure that all involved actors such as the private sector and citizens can contribute but also benefit from the emerging data spaces should be clarified [19].

Ethical data management:

- Use Protocols: One way to acknowledge community ownership is to require that data users agree to specific protocols for use prior to gaining access to data, for example [21]:
 - DataStream and AAOKH ask users to agree to use requirements including proper attribution prior to downloading data.
 - The SIKU platform, a mobile app and web platform that provides services for ice safety, uses terms of reference to place the responsibility on platform contributors to have data access agreements and licensing in place.
- Address Injustice and power imbalances:
 - Indigenous data sovereignty: When data is managed ethically, digital platforms can serve as tools to support Indigenous data sovereignty, ensuring that data is available for local use and under control of local stewards [10], [21], [29].
 - Example: The Clyde River Knowledge Atlas (clyderiveratlas.ca) was established by Inuit residents of Clyde River, Nunavut, Canada, to ensure that information from research and monitoring conducted in Clyde River was available to residents [21].
 - Digital mapping platforms for Indigenous land rights, which focus directly on the rights of the involved peoples and communities, may also provide examples of ethical data management practices for the community based monitoring (CBM) community [21].
 - Looking at power imbalances – for example specific histories of injustice, such as colonial histories and negative past relationships between Indigenous people and universities – is typically not something that data modellers (a professional who specialises in designing and creating data models) do, but something that could be implemented as a practice and that would be helpful to include in the data biography [40].
- Networking Activities: Facilitate networking activities among platforms to specifically address how community-level priorities and concerns can inform broader scientific, observing, and decision-making efforts [21].
- Provide utility for users collecting data: identify and address the potential volunteers' questions or needs that can be resolved from the data. Avoid only focusing on providing utility of data just for researchers [24].
- Return on Participation: Volunteers need “something in return”, from simple data download to publication of aggregated relevant results. One way of addressing this is by supporting the publication of at least metadata of the project in a repository or searchable database [23].
- Respecting community data ownership: Every community's expectation will be different and researchers should be mindful of the sense of ownership that community members may feel toward data that they were responsible for collecting. Researchers should share data in a manner that respects the wishes of the community in which it was collected [4].
- User deletion options: Users should have the option to delete personal information if collected [5], [63], [68]. One example to highlight: Registered members of PatientsLikeMe own the data that they upload and can choose to keep their data on the platform, or delete their data while keeping their account open, or voluntarily close their account but agree to the data being hosted for 3 years or delete their account and permanently delete all information about them.

PatientsLikeMe explains how it profits commercially from data supplied by the community [55].

- Flexible citizen science project governance: CitSci.org (a citizen science platform) believes that decisions related to the governance of citizen science initiatives are usually best left to each project. The platform offers flexible options for sharing data and membership of the projects. Close, open, and mixed models in data access depending on the type of project are needed. Also, options of different models of membership to projects (close, open, under invitation). They consider a default global “open” setting for sharing data and joining a project would restrict participation on the platform [64].

Lessons learned

Ethical and Privacy Concerns:

- Volunteer exploitation: Exploitation of volunteers could occur if the volunteers do not receive a share of benefits potentially obtained by the research they participated in. The scientist should aim at sharing IPR, authorship, formal recognition, education, or monetary value [23], [40], [46].
- Late data licensing: Data licensing is often not considered until late in the project, which may cause confusion between volunteers and project management [23].
- Insurance coverage: Insurance coverage conditions are often unclear when doing research including volunteers, in contrast to research subjects, who in Denmark, for example, are covered by the public patient or work injury insurances [23]
- Informed consent: In the European Commission survey on data management only 10 projects (8%) out of those surveyed asked their participants to sign an explicit informed consent form [55].
- Unclear agreements: Unclear agreements on data ownership and use exist in some research and citizen science programs [63].
- Privacy violations: Personal data are often repurposed in ways violating privacy and ethics [40].
- Exclusion of underrepresented groups: Citizen science projects can sometimes involve only specific segments of society, potentially excluding historically underrepresented groups, less wealthy individuals, and people from certain socioeconomic, racial, and ethnic backgrounds. This exclusion may impact the quality of outcomes [29].
- Age restriction: Due to the inability of iNaturalist, a citizen science platform, to guarantee that participants under the age of 13 won't share personal information on the website, which would be against the law, the platform has implemented an age restriction policy. As a result, only individuals who are 18 years old or older are allowed to participate on iNaturalist [66]. This condition limits participation and engagement of children and young people.

Transparency and fairness:

- Opaque Models: Commonly-used predictive machine learning methods are notoriously opaque,

though this can vary for the specific model in question. Sometimes algorithms become self-fulfilling prophecies which disproportionately affect vulnerable populations, with no recourse to appeal opaque decisions due to the often proprietary nature of the models. Interdisciplinary engagement between people in charge of data modelling, with technical skills for working with big data, and science and technology studies (STS) scholars, with skills for critiquing the processes of science, could be a fruitful way to move towards these kinds of tools [40].

- Not all data processes are presently transparent or open to the public or potential participants [55].
- Algorithm auditing: Researchers are exploring methods for auditing algorithms. Access Now and Amnesty International created a Declaration for protecting rights to equality and non-discrimination in machine learning systems. Modellers and organisations can subscribe to such declarations as a commitment to addressing impacts and implications of their work. Interdisciplinary collaboration with critical scholars can help modellers investigate potential benefits and harms in project design and implementation [40].
- Private-sector data: It is still to be understood how to best reuse private sector data in a way that is to the maximum extent possible beneficial for all stakeholders. Difficulties include [19], [26]:
 - Absence of a clear regulatory framework requiring the private sector to contribute their data across multiple domains.
 - Limited societal benefits: Societal benefits from their possible reuse remain limited.
 - Anonymisation measures: Specific measures for anonymisation shall be put in place.
 - Fear of lawsuits: Fear that opening up datasets could pave the way for future lawsuits.
- Public sector role: How to make the most out of the scattered resources while retaining sovereignty from big software platforms is to be addressed. Whatever the possible solution, the public sector has an important role to play [19].

Key resources

- **Data ethics toolkit:** A toolkit for data ethics in the participatory sciences. The toolkit is a comprehensive guide designed to help navigate the complex world of data ethics and ensure that research is conducted in a responsible and trustworthy manner¹².
- **Data Ethics Canvas:** it is a versatile tool applicable to individuals involved in data collection, sharing, or utilisation. It assists in recognising and addressing ethical concerns from the beginning of a data-driven project and throughout its lifecycle¹³.

¹² <https://citizenscience.org/data-ethics/>

¹³ <https://www.theodi.org/article/the-data-ethics-canvas-2021/#1674123644668-d213eb86-71e4>

- **Managing intellectual property rights in citizen science:** This document explores intellectual property (IP) concerns in citizen science projects from the perspectives of researchers, participants, and the general public¹⁴.

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<https://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/managing-intellectual-property-rights-citizen-science-guide-for-researchers-and-citizen>

Considerations

Considering the mapping of co-designing citizen science data infrastructures and services using established best practices, the following can be highlighted:

- The document underscores the importance of developing detailed and context-specific proven practices. While there may be limited documentation in certain areas, it is crucial to recognise the value of documenting experiences and best practices in specific contexts. Each citizen science project or initiative operates within a unique set of circumstances, such as the subject matter, target audience, or available resources. By documenting and sharing proven practices in these specific contexts, we can provide valuable insights and guidance to practitioners facing similar challenges. This approach enables the transfer of knowledge and fosters continuous improvement, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness and impact of citizen science efforts. Encouraging the documentation and dissemination of detailed proven practices will contribute to a more robust and informed citizen science community.
- In addition to documenting proven practices, the mapping of co-designing citizen science data infrastructures and data services highlights the importance of capturing lessons learned from practices that did not work as expected. Often, unsuccessful or failed practices receive less attention in research and documentation efforts. However, understanding what did not work and the reasons behind it can be just as valuable as studying successful practices. By examining failures and challenges encountered during co-design processes, practitioners can avoid repeating the same mistakes, identify potential pitfalls, and gain a deeper understanding of the complexities involved. Including a focus on lessons learned from unsuccessful practices in the documentation adds significant value by providing a more comprehensive understanding of the co-design landscape in citizen science.
- There is a concerning lack of documentation and limited references regarding co-design and co-development experiences. This could indicate a lack of documented experiences in this specific field or a potential lack of awareness about the importance of documenting such practices. The scarcity of available resources and references on co-design and co-development practices suggests a need for increased efforts to document and share experiences in order to facilitate knowledge exchange and provide guidance for future initiatives.
- The report raises important questions about the lack of discussion and documentation regarding data security in the context of citizen science. It is unclear whether the limited reference is due to a lack of experience or a lack of documentation. Possible reasons for this gap could include the complexity of legal requirements surrounding data security, a lack of awareness among practitioners, or a need for greater emphasis on data security within the citizen science community. To ensure the responsible and secure management of citizen science data, it is imperative to address data security considerations explicitly. This includes developing clear guidelines, protocols, and best practices to protect the privacy and confidentiality of participants' data, while also enabling open and collaborative research. Efforts should be made to close this gap and promote greater awareness and understanding of data security principles in the context of citizen science.

Key resources list

Data infrastructure

- Data interoperability: A practitioner's guide to joining up data in the development sector.
<https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/handle/11329/1971>
- European Data Spaces - Scientific Insights into Data Sharing and Utilisation at Scale.
<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129900>

Data services

- Co-design as a service: Methodological guide.
https://zenodo.org/record/7472450#.Y_52Oa2ZOs-

Data collection

- Data management guide for public participation in scientific research -DataONE-
<https://dataoneorg.github.io/Education/bestpractices/>
- Data management planning for citizen science.
<https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/handle/11329/1406>

Data standards

- Public Participation in Scientific Research-Core (PPSR-Core) project.
<https://core.citizenscience.org/>
- Research data management challenges in citizen science projects and recommendations for library support services.
<https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2021-025>

Data quality assurance

- Still in need of norms: The state of the data in citizen science.
<https://theoryandpractice.citizenscienceassociation.org/articles/10.5334/cstp.303>
- Data Quality in Citizen Science.
https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_8

Data accessibility

- Guide to Data Charter for Citizen Science.
<https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/data-charter-and-guide-citizen-science>

Data ownership

- Data ethics toolkit: a toolkit for data ethics in the participatory sciences.
<https://citizenscience.org/data-ethics/>

- Data Ethics Canvas.
<https://www.theodi.org/article/the-data-ethics-canvas-2021/#1674123644668-d213eb86-71e4>
- Managing intellectual property rights in citizen science.
<https://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/managing-intellectual-property-rights-citizen-science-guide-for-researchers-and-citizen>

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